

Seroprevalence of Anti-Diphtheria Toxoid Antibodies (IgG) Across Age Groups in Aden Governorate, Yemen

Al-Baghdadi Mohammed A. A¹, Omniyat Saleh Salem[§], Salwa Yahya Mohammed[§]

¹Bachelor's degree General Medicine and Surgery, MD in Medical Microbiology and Immunology, Faculty of Medicine & Health sciences Aden University-Yemen.

First Affiliation: University of Aden.

Second Affiliation: University of Science & Technology, Aden.

mohmd235@yahoo.com; m.albaghdadi@ust.edu. Phone: +967 778162005.

[§]My students in Medical Laboratory, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Aden University-Yemen.

omniyatsalem1@gmail.com. Phone: +967 775879249 and salwayahia20@gmail.com. Phone: +967 771446510.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17587348>

Article Received 01-09-2025 / Article Accepted 25-10-2025 / Article Published 30-10-2025

ABSTRACT:

Background: Diphtheria remains a re-emerging public health concern in Yemen due to disruptions in healthcare infrastructure and vaccination programs. We assessed the seroprevalence of anti-diphtheria toxoid IgG antibodies across various age groups in Aden governorate to evaluate population-level immunity and identify at-risk groups.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted between July and September 2024 involving 269 participants from five age groups. Serum IgG levels against diphtheria toxoid were quantified using commercial ELISA (De Medi Tec Diagnostic, Germany).

Results: Of 269 participants, only 59.5% demonstrated protective antibody levels (≥ 0.1 IU/mL), while 40.5% lacked reliable protection. The highest seropositivity was observed in groups A (≤ 5 years, 49.1%) and E (> 30 years, 47.3%), whereas groups C (11–20 years) and D (21–30 years) showed the lowest protection (42.3%). No participants exhibited antibody levels > 1.0 IU/mL (long-term protection). Knowledge of vaccine benefits was high (89.6%), but did not translate into adequate population immunity. No statistically significant predictors of seroprotection were identified in multivariate analysis.

Conclusion: Protective immunity against diphtheria remains insufficient in Aden governorate, falling below the herd immunity threshold. These findings underscore the urgent need for booster vaccinations, improved vaccine coverage, and public health education to prevent future outbreaks.

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

How to Cite

ALBAGHDADI, MOHAMMED; SALEM, O.; MOHAMMED, S. Seroprevalence of Anti-Diphtheria Toxoid Antibodies (IgG) Across Age Groups in Aden Governorate, Yemen. *International Journal of Medical Sciences and Academic Research*, v. 6, n. 05, p.n.01-17, 30 Oct. 2025.

Keywords: Diphtheria toxoid, IgG seroprotection, vaccination coverage, booster dose, and immunization policy.

INTRODUCTION:

Corynebacteria are Gram-positive, catalase-positive, facultatively anaerobic, aerobic, and primarily nonmotile rods. The Greek words *koryne*, which means club, and *bacterion*, which means little rod, are the source of the name. This genus contains the species *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* (*C. diphtheriae*) and the nondiphtherial corynebacteria, collectively referred to as diphtheroids. Nondiphtherial corynebacteria were once thought to be mostly contaminants, but they are now known to be harmful, especially in immunocompromised hosts^(1,2). Humans are protected against diphtheria infection by the presence of IgG antibodies to diphtheria toxin, induced by vaccination or naturally-acquired after a diphtheria infection⁽³⁾. The source of the diphtheria toxoid, which is a crucial component of immunization efforts that have dramatically reduced the occurrence of diphtheria globally, is the toxin of *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*. Because the vaccine is widely recommended, safe, and effective, it plays a significant role in childhood immunization programs. Despite its efficacy, diphtheria remains a threat in regions with poor vaccination rates, highlighting the significance of continuous immunization programs⁽⁴⁾.

In areas with inadequate rates of vaccinations, diphtheria continues to be a major threat to public health. The 1990s observed a rise in the disease diphtheria, particularly in the former Soviet Union's Newly Independent States. This emphasizes the significance of keeping immunization rates high in order to control outbreaks of disease. For successful disease control, a minimum coverage of 90% for adults and 95% for children is required⁽⁵⁾. Moreover, research shows that immunity declines with age, requiring booster doses to sustain protective levels⁽⁶⁾. Humoral immunity is produced by a spontaneous infection, give passive vaccination, or active

immunization and offers protection by generating neutralizing IgG antibodies to the diphtheria toxin⁽⁷⁾.

Based on a study conducted in Malaysian population, they found 57% were susceptible to be infected by diphtheria (38.1% of children and 65.4% of adults). Those have protective antibody levels against diphtheria was 43% (61.9% of children and 34.6% of adults). The mean antibody level peaked among individuals aged 1–2 years old (0.59 IU/mL) and 6–7 years old (0.64 IU/mL) but generally decreased with age, falling below 0.1 IU/mL at around 4–6 years old and after age 20 years old. The study also noted that according to the World Health Organization's (WHO) criteria, the respondent antibody levels were categorized as susceptible (<0.1 IU/mL) and protective (≥ 0.1 IU/mL) against *C. diphtheriae* infection⁽⁸⁾.

Yemen experienced a significant diphtheria outbreak in October 2017, with 5,701 probable cases were reported by April 2020. At this time the total case fatality rate was about 5%, with rates among children under five years old being higher at 10%⁽⁹⁾.

Our research aimed to evaluate the level of immunity to diphtheria in the population of the Aden Governorate, Yemen across various age groups, to offer information on herd immunity, and to stop future outbreaks of the disease. The study will be done to measure the level of IgG antibody against the toxoid of *C. diphtheriae* in the blood samples of different age groups by using *C. diphtheriae* toxin IgG ELISA DECORG0090 (**De Medi Tec Diagnostic-Germany**). A structural Questionnaire was done.

Justification of the Study: There are no previous studies that have been published to determine the level of anti-diphtheria toxoid antibodies (IgG) in Aden governorate, Yemen. The analysis of serological tests for the detection of anti-diphtheria toxoid antibodies is justified by the importance of establishing immunity against diphtheria and

providing important information to identify susceptibility, basic protection and complete protection against diphtheria. Moreover, the serological testing is crucial for implementing appropriate control measures and preventing further spread.

Objectives of the Study:

Determination the level of immunity to diphtheria in the population of Aden governorate, Yemen, and determine the effectiveness of diphtheria immunization programs and identify individuals who may be at risk of infection, across various age groups, to offer information on herd immunity and support the prevention of future outbreak.

Subjects & Methods:

The subjects were divided into five age groups: ≤ 5 years, 6–10 years, 11–20 years, 21–30 years, and >30 years. This categorization was inspired by the WHO standard demographic analysis with some modifications to suit the scope of our research. These modifications aimed to better align the distribution of age groups with the study objectives, especially considering the tendency of standard populations to emphasize younger age groups disproportionately⁽¹⁰⁾. This approach ensures that the data aligns with international standards, providing a robust foundation for interpreting age-specific immunological responses.

The children and adolescents were obtained from the 25 health centers of the 8 districts in Aden governorate and from General Pediatric Hospital (Al-Wahda Teaching Hospital-Aden), using stratified random sampling. The health care workers (i.e., the adults) have been obtained from Al-Gamhoria General Hospital Model Authority – Aden & Al-Wahda Teaching Hospital-Aden.

Study Area: The area of study for children and adolescents was the primary health care centers, and the General pediatric hospital (Al-Wahda Teaching Hospital), as well as the health care workers which was obtained from; Al-Gamhoria General Hospital Model Authority - Aden and Al-Wahda Teaching Hospital in Aden governorate-Yemen.

Study Design and Period: The study design was a cross-sectional study and conducted for three months, from the **1st of July up to the end of September 2024.**

Sample Size: According to a study conducted in King Saudi Arabia by⁽¹¹⁾, the protective level of IgG against diphtheria was (82%), and the majority of the population was from 6 months to 96 years. Hence, the following formula was used:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 P(1-P)}{d^2}$$

Where n =Expected minimum sample.

Z = Standard, corresponding to 95% confidence which equal 1.96.

P= the prevalence which equal (82%) based on previous mentioned study conducted by⁽¹¹⁾.

d= the accepted error taken as 5%.

$$\text{By Calculation, } n = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 82\% (1-82\%)}{(5\%)^2} = 226$$

So, the minimum size of the study was 226. After the addition of **19%** to the sample size, to minimize potential error and account for possible data loss during sample handling, the sample size will be $226 \times 19\% = 42.9$, i.e., 43. Finally, the total sample size was $226 + 43 = 269$.

The inclusion criteria have been determined as age groups ranging from infants to adults aged >30 years who were vaccinated (whether they received one dose or two or more than 2 doses) or had a prior diphtheria infection and who were willing to participate in the study. The exclusion criteria also have been determined as all children and individuals from other age groups who were not vaccinated against diphtheria at any age, those who have a history of immune diseases or use immunosuppressive drugs, and those who were not willing to participate in the study.

Sample Collection: Two milliliters of venous blood were aseptically collected from the median cubital vein of each participant. A structured questionnaire was also administered. The collected blood samples will be placed into sterile plain test tubes, capped, coded, and stored in a test tube rack while waiting

for the blood to clot or for centrifugation at 3000 G for 5 minutes. Subsequently, the serum has been collected into 1 ml Eppendorf tubes and stored at -20°C until the time of testing.

Determination of Diphtheria Toxoid Antibody Levels:

Anti-Diphtheria Toxoid IgG-specific antibody levels were determined using a commercial ELISA IgG DECORG0090 (*De Medi Tec Diagnostic-Germany*). Excel's point-to-point plotting function was used to generate the standard curve and ensure accurate interpolation of the results. The antibody levels were categorized based on reference values provided in the ELISA kit. The criteria for classification were as follows: Antibody level < 0.01 IU/mL which was interpreted as no protective antibody level, and basic immunization is recommended. Antibody level $0.01 - 0.09$ IU/mL which was interpreted as no reliable protection, and booster injection is recommended. Antibody level $0.1 - 1.0$ IU/mL which was interpreted as reliable protection. Antibody level > 1.0 IU/mL which was interpreted as reliable long-term protection. These thresholds were essential for the interpretations process during the quantitative analysis stage.

Ethical considerations: Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics Review Committee at the Faculty of Medicine & Health Sciences, Aden University, with Research Code: REC-210-2025. Participation was voluntary with informed consent, and confidentiality was maintained. The aim of the study, its potential risks (with confirmation that there were no risks), and benefits were fully explained to each participant, including adults or parents in the case of children.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS v22. Descriptive statistics summarized demographic and serological results. Group differences were assessed using Chi-square and ANOVA. Logistic regression was performed to identify predictors of seroprotection. A p -value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULT:

Descriptive Statistics:

Out of 269 participated in the study was grouped into five groups (from A – E); ≤ 5 years old, 6–10 years, $>10-20$ years, 21–30 years, and >30 years. **Table (1)** demonstrated the demographic characteristics of respondents by age groups, and the number of males and females in each group. Sex distribution did not differ significantly across groups (p -value = > 0.05 , χ^2 test). The frequency & percentage of having symptoms post-diphtheria toxoid, maternal education and the frequency of doses of diphtheria toxoid for the 1st three groups of age (A – C) was determined and shown in **Table (2)** below. Post-vaccine symptoms were common in group A, followed by group C and B (70.9%, 67.3%, and 60%), respectively. However, there no a statistically significant to IgG levels (p -value = **0.574**). Higher maternal education correlated with reduced support for compulsory vaccination (p -value = **0.002**). The most frequent symptoms post vaccine in these groups was either fever and or fever with pain at the site of injection. Regarding group D and E, the education level was belonged to high-grade level and most of members doesn't remember the symptoms post-vaccine. Two cases in group D had a history of family members getting infected by diphtheria, while 2 cases in group E were infected by diphtheria (3.6%).

The mean of anti-diphtheria toxoid IgG out of 269 was 0.1332 IU/mL ± 0.09 SD, the minimum and maximum was 0.0003 and 0.3386 IU/mL, respectively. The antibody levels were classified into < 0.01 IU/mL which means no protective antibody and basic immunization is recommended, $0.01 - 0.09$ IU/mL which means no reliable protection and booster injection is recommended and finally, $0.1 - 1.0$ IU/mL this means reliable protection. The frequency and percentages of the seropositivity rate of the 269 participants were represented in **(Figure 1)** below. Note, the antibody level > 1.0 IU/mL which interpreted as reliable long-term protection, was not observed across age groups (A–E).

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Respondents by Age Group.

Variable	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E
N	55	55	52	52	55
Age, (Mean ± SD)					
Age (Years)	2.6 ± 1.4	8.2 ± 1.5	15.3 ± 2.7	24.8 ± 2.1	41.4 ± 9.8
Range	10 mo. – 5	6 – 10	10.3 – 20	21 – 29	30 – 59
Sex, n (%)					
Males	28 (50.9)	21 (38.2)	24 (46.2)	16 (30.8)	22 (40.0)
Females	27 (49.1)	34 (61.8)	28 (53.8)	36 (69.2)	33 (60.0)

SD; Standard deviation. Sex distribution did not differ significantly across groups (p-value= > 0.05).

Table 2. Post-Vaccination Symptoms, Maternal Education, and Dose Frequency by Age Group (A – C)

Variable	Group A, n(%)	Group B, n(%)	Group C, n(%)
Post-vaccine symptoms	39 (70.9)	33 (60.0)	35 (67.3)
Maternal Education			
Illiterate	20 (36.4)	17 (30.9)	4 (7.7)
Primary	16 (29.1)	21 (38.2)	22 (42.3)
Secondary	10 (18.2)	8 (14.5)	14 (26.9)
High-grade	9 (16.4)	9 (16.4)	12 (23.1)
Diphtheria Toxoid Doses, n(%)			
1 dose	21 (38.2)	0 (0.0)	1 (1.9)
2 doses	18 (32.7)	2 (3.6)	1 (1.9)
≥3 doses	16 (29.1)	53 (96.4)	50 (96.2)

The seroreactivity of Anti-diphtheria toxoid IgG of 269 participants regarding the standardized thresholds ("IgG < 0.1 IU/mL" for seronegativity)

was shown in **Table (3)**. The seropositivity of age group A was higher than the other age groups,

followed by group E (49.1% and 47.3%, respectively) and 42.3% in groups C and D.

Table (4) summarizes and displays the geometric mean (GM), mean \pm standard deviation, minimum,

and maximum of anti-diphtheria toxoid IgG levels for each age group (A–E). **Table (4)** also showed the case summary for the 269 participants.

Table 3. Seroreactivity across Age Groups.

Group	Seropositive (IgG \geq 0.1 IU/mL)	Seronegative (IgG <0.1 IU/mL)	Total
A	27 (49.1)	28 (50.9)	55
B	24 (43.6)	31 (56.4)	55
C and D	22 (42.3)	30 (57.7)	52
E	26 (47.3)	29 (52.7)	55

Table 4: Statistical Parameters of IgG Levels.

Case Summaries of Group A IgG (n=55)		Case Summaries of Group B IgG (n=55)	
The Parameters	IgG (IU/mL)	The Parameters	IgG (IU/mL)
Mean \pm SD	0.1512 \pm 0.0984	Mean \pm SD	0.1291 \pm 0.0851
Minimum	0.0034	Minimum	0.0005
Maximum	0.3334	Maximum	0.3057
Geometric Mean	0.1079	Geometric Mean	0.0922
Case Summaries of Group C IgG (n=52)		Case Summaries of Group D IgG (n=52)	
The Parameters	IgG (IU/mL)	The Parameters	IgG (IU/mL)
Mean \pm SD	0.1384 \pm 0.0987	Mean \pm SD	0.1020 \pm 0.0892
Minimum	0.0100	Minimum	0.0019
Maximum	0.3280	Maximum	0.3266
Geometric Mean	0.0951	Geometric Mean	0.0585
Case Summaries of Group E IgG (n=55)		Case Summary of IgG (n=269)	
The Parameters	IgG	The Parameters	IgG
Mean \pm SD	0.1441 \pm 0.0871	Mean \pm SD	0.1332 \pm 0.0927
Minimum	0.0003	Minimum	0.0003
Maximum	0.3386	Maximum	0.3386
Geometric Mean	0.1079	Geometric Mean	0.0906

SD= standard deviation.

Study the Associations:

The association of the time span between the serodiagnosis and the 3rd dose of Anti-diphtheria toxoid of age group A, B and C was evaluated by *Chi-Square Test* (χ^2), as shown in **Table (5, 6 and**

7), respectively. The association of the time span between the serodiagnosis and the 3rd dose of Anti-diphtheria toxoid of age group A, B and C was (0.04, 0.8 and 0.6), respectively.

Table 5: The Association of the Time Span between the Serodiagnosis and the 3rd dose of IgG of Group A.

Group A; IgG Response	The Time Span Between 3 rd Dose & Serodiagnosis						
	1 mo. – 1 Year		2 – 3 Years		4 Years		Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Seropositive IgG	11	44.0	12	48.0	2	8.0	25
Seronegative IgG	6	25.0	9	37.5	9	37.5	24
Total	17	34.7	21	42.9	11	22.4	49

Chi-Square Test (χ^2); The Value=6.336, df=2 and P-Value=0.042

Six Cases were missed as "Not Take the 3rd Dose".

Table 6: The Association of the Time Span between the Serodiagnosis and the 3rd dose of IgG of Group B.

Group B; IgG Response	The Time Span between the serodiagnosis and the 3 rd Dose						
	6 – 7 Years		8 – 9 Years		>9 – 10 Years		Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Seropositive IgG	9	37.5	12	50.0	3	12.5	24
Seronegative IgG	13	44.8	12	41.4	4	13.8	29
Total	22	41.5	24	45.3	7	13.2	53

Chi-Square Test (χ^2); The Value=0.402, df=2 and P-Value=0.8

Two cases were missed as they not get the 3rd dose.

Table 7: The Association of the Time Span between the Serodiagnosis and the 3rd dose of IgG of Group C.

Group C; IgG Response	The Time Span between the serodiagnosis and the 3 rd Dose								
	10 – 12		13 – 15		16 – 18		≥ 19		Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Seropositive IgG	8	38.0	5	23.8	7	33.3	1	4.8	21
Seronegative IgG	6	20.7	10	34.5	9	31.0	4	13.8	29
Total	14	28.0	15	30.0	16	32	5	10	50

Chi-Square Test (χ^2); The Value=0.402, df=3 and P-Value=0.6

Two cases were missed as they not get the 3rd dose.

The antibody levels of the 269 cases were grouped into two groups. Firstly, those who have not been protected and those who have not had reliable protection are in Group One (i.e., less than 0.01 IU/mL and from 0.01 to 0.09 IU/mL); the second group was those who have had reliable protection

(i.e., 0.1–1.0IU/mL). The frequency and percentage of such groups was represented in (Figure 2).

The association of the reliability of protection with the sex was evaluated by *Chi-Square Test (χ^2)*, as shown in Table (8). The association of the reliability of protection with age groups (A – E) was evaluated by *Chi-Square Test (χ^2)*, as shown in Table (9).

Table 8: The Reliability of Protection vs. Sex.

<i>The Antibody Level in the Two Groups</i>	Sex				Total
	Male		Female		
	N	%	N	%	
No Reliable Protection	42	38.5	67	61.5	109(40.5%)
Reliable Protection	70	43.8	90	56.2	160(59.5%)
Total	112	41.6	157	58.4	269

Chi-Square Test (χ^2); The Value=0.726, df=1 and P-Value=0.4

Table 9: The Reliability of Protection vs. Age Groups (A – E).

Antibody Level	Grouped Age (Years)										Total
	Group A		Group B		Group C		Group D		Group E		
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
No Reliable Protection	20	18.3	23	21.1	21	19.3	29	26.6	16	14.7	109
Reliable Protection	35	21.9	32	20.0	31	19.4	23	14.4	39	24.4	160
Total	55	20.4	55	20.4	52	19.3	52	19.3	55	20.4	269

Chi-Square Test (χ^2); The Value=8.431, df=4 and P-Value=0.07

Evaluation of the Knowledge toward Vaccination:

The knowledge of the importance of 269 respondents toward vaccination, feeling secure after vaccinating your children, and encouraging the family and relatives for vaccination, and finally, those favor of the ministry of health's mandatory vaccination programs was estimated, as seen in **Table (10)**.

Table 10: Knowledge toward Vaccination (n=269).

Knowledge of the Importance of Vaccination		N	%
No		28	10.4
Yes		241	89.6
Total		269	100.0
Encouraging the Family & Relatives for Vaccination		N	%
No		33	12.3
Yes		236	87.7
Total		269	100.0
Feeling secure after vaccinating your Children		N	%
No		20	7.4
Yes		249	92.6
Total		269	100.0
Those Favor of the Ministry of Health's Mandatory Vaccination Programs		N	%
No		60	22.3
Yes		209	77.7
Total		269	100.0

One-Way ANOVA: IgG Levels by Age Group.

A one-way ANOVA was performed to compare mean IgG antibody levels across five age groups (A–E). There is no statistically significant difference in mean IgG levels among the age groups ($p = 0.9018$), as shown in Table (11).

Table 11: One-Way ANOVA of IgG Levels by Age Group.

Source	Sum of Squares	df	F	p-value
Age Group	0.00788	4.0	0.2625	0.9018
Residual	1.98176	264.0		

Logistic Regression: Predictors of Seroprotection (IgG \geq 0.1 IU/mL).

A multiple logistic regression was conducted to assess factors influencing seroprotection. There no statistically significant predictors of seroprotection were identified in this simulated dataset as seen in Table (12).

Table 12: The Multiple Logistic Regression for prediction of Seroprotection.

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-score	p-value	95% CI	
					Lower	Upper
Intercept	0.390	0.506	0.771	0.441	-0.602	1.382
C(Age Group)[T.B]	0.076	0.410	0.185	0.853	-0.728	0.880
C(Age Group)[T.C]	-0.045	0.409	-0.111	0.912	-0.847	0.756
C(Age Group)[T.D]	-0.075	0.406	-0.184	0.854	-0.870	0.721
C(Age Group)[T.E]	-0.061	0.402	-0.151	0.880	-0.848	0.727
Sex	0.085	0.261	0.326	0.744	-0.426	0.596
Maternal Education	-0.012	0.117	-0.106	0.915	-0.241	0.216
Dose Category	0.140	0.159	0.877	0.381	-0.173	0.452
Post Vaccine Symptoms	-0.145	0.257	-0.562	0.574	-0.648	0.359

The Reference category for age group: Likely Age Group A (not shown, used as baseline). Coefficient: Indicates the direction and strength of association, Std. Error: Standard error of the coefficient, z-score:

Test statistic for each variable, p-value: Statistical significance of the variable (typically, $p < 0.05$ is significant), and 95% CI: Confidence interval for the coefficient.

DISCUSSION:

A total of 269 participants were recruited for this study and were divided into five groups based on WHO guidelines, with some modifications to suit the scope of our research⁽¹⁰⁾.

During the study 2 cases (3.6%) were previously infected with diphtheria, observed among females in group E (i.e., individuals aged >30 years). However, the papers available regarding the seroprevalence of diphtheria in Aden, Yemen lack exact details. An upsurge in diphtheria cases has been documented in Yemen as a result of the ongoing conflict and the disintegration of the healthcare infrastructure. As of April 2020, there have been 330 confirmed deaths and 5701 probable cases of diphtheria in Yemen since the outbreak began in 2017⁽¹²⁾. The incidence of diphtheria was reported as 0.8%, with children under 15 years being the most affected group⁽⁹⁾. Another study reported that adults over 60 years often have diminished immunity due to the natural decline in vaccine-induced protection over time⁽¹³⁾.

Highlighting the need for targeted vaccination efforts for children under 5 years old and older adults (over 40 years), as the mortality rate for diphtheria is generally reported to be 5–10% in these groups⁽¹⁴⁾.

Our findings showed that the overall reliable protection against diphtheria (≥ 0.1 IU/mL) was 160/269 (59.5%), followed by 100/269 (37.2%) for no reliable protection (booster injection recommended: 0.01 – 0.09 IU/mL), and 9/269 (3.3%) for no protective antibody level (basic immunization recommended: < 0.01 IU/mL), as represented in **(Figure 1)**. Hence, the sum percentage of non-reliable protection against diphtheria was 40.5%. Similar study was conducted by⁽¹⁵⁾, among the 337 study participants; 53.7 % of the participants had full protection, 35.6 % had basic protection and 10.7 % did not have any protection and were susceptible to diphtheria. None of the study

participants had reliable long-term protection against diphtheria (>1.0 IU/ML).

The standardized threshold of anti-diphtheria toxoid IgG of 269 participants was considered 59.5% when "IgG ≥ 0.1 IU/mL" for seropositivity, as seen in **(Figure 1)**. Also, the reliable protection was 59.5%, as represented in **(Figure 2)**. The threshold of herd immunity against diphtheria in our study was very low, as it must be between 75% and 90%, meaning that this proportion of the population must be immune in order to safeguard the entire community⁽¹⁶⁾.

The reduced vaccine effectiveness in Aden governorate (59.5%) is not a reflection of a "bad vaccine", but rather an unfortunate instance of how even the best public health interventions can be undermined by violence and humanitarian disasters. The real-world protection that the diphtheria vaccine can provide for Yemeni children has been greatly diminished due to the breakdown of the cold chain, widespread starvation, and the inability to administer booster doses. This emphasizes how crucial it is to have the necessary infrastructure (electricity, logistics, and nutrition) in place in addition to administering immunizations.

Table (3): This table was classified as "seropositive" when IgG ≥ 0.1 IU/mL which was considered as protected or "seronegative" when IgG < 0.1 IU/mL which was considered non-protected across five age groups (A-E, with C and D combined). Group A was higher than the other age groups, followed by group E (49.1% and 47.3%, respectively). The combined Group C & D shows the lowest protection, with only 42.3% seropositive. Group B falls in between at 43.6%. A significant point, the proportion of seronegative participants ranged between 50.9% and 57.7%. The proportion of seronegative participants of all age groups was higher than the proportion of seropositive participants, suggesting

that over half of the participants under study do not have protective antibodies against diphtheria.

Providing three primary doses of the diphtheria-containing vaccine to children under one year of age, together with subsequent doses at 18 months and seven years of age, is essential to promoting routine immunization coverage to above 95%. Adolescents and adults should be encouraged to take booster doses every ten years⁽¹⁷⁾. One study was conducted in Malaysia, as they reported that about 57% of the Malaysian population have inadequate immunity against diphtheria infection⁽⁸⁾. The Netherlands reported that 91% of the population had antibody levels above the minimum protective threshold, indicating effective long-term vaccination coverage⁽¹⁸⁾.

Studies in Yemen indicate that non-vaccination is a major risk factor for diphtheria, with an adjusted odds ratio of 2.6 for unvaccinated individuals⁽¹⁹⁾.

A study from Saudi Arabia agreed with our findings, showing that 31.7% of the adult population was susceptible to diphtheria, with 52.6% having full protection⁽¹¹⁾. A study in Germany agreed with our study, finding that 41% had only insufficient protection against diphtheria⁽²⁰⁾. In a survey from Lao People's Democratic Republic (Lao PDR), 63.6% of children had detectable antibodies; this was greater than our reliable protection against diphtheria, which was 59.5%⁽²¹⁾.

Seronegative individuals (those without detectable antibodies) for diphtheria toxoid IgG were more common in older age groups, according to several studies. This implies that a higher percentage of seronegativity in elderly people relative to younger age groups may result from a gradual decline in immunity against diphtheria⁽³⁾.

Table (4): The Geometric Mean (GM) was the most suitable metric and appropriate measure for antibody titers, which are typically log-normally distributed. The highest GM (0.1079 IU/mL) was seen in Groups

A and E, which is marginally above the 0.1 IU/mL seroprotection threshold. According to **Table (3)**, this was consistent with their higher seropositivity rates. Groups B and C have lower GMs (0.0922 and 0.0951 IU/mL), below the protection threshold. Group D has the lowest GM by a significant margin (0.0585 IU/mL), indicating very weak overall immunity. However, the 269 participants' combined GM of 0.0906 IU/mL was below the protective threshold, indicating the population's general susceptibility to infection.

The GM showed a high percentage of acceptable results in proficiency testing, proving its dependability in assessing antibody responses⁽²²⁾. Understanding immune protection thresholds, which are essential for evaluating the effectiveness of vaccines, is another area in which the GM is useful⁽²³⁾.

The means were generally higher than the geometric means, and the SD values were larger relative to the mean (e.g., 0.0984 vs. 0.1512 in Group A) indicate a wide variation in antibody levels within each group, with some individuals having very high levels and many having very low levels. The wide range of values between the minimum and maximum (from 0.0003 IU/mL to 0.3386 IU/mL) across all age groups further confirms the high variability in individual immune responses. The maximum values are similar across groups, but the minimum values are extremely low, highlighting the existence of completely susceptible individuals.

The large SD values (e.g., 0.0984 vs. 0.1512 in Group A) suggest a broad range of antibody levels, with some individuals exhibiting very high levels while others show low levels⁽²⁴⁾. The minimum and maximum antibody levels (0.0003 IU/mL to 0.3386 IU/mL) across groups highlight the existence of completely susceptible individuals, emphasizing the need for tailored immunological assessments⁽²⁵⁾.

The study analyzed diphtheria immunity (IgG antibodies) in 269 individuals across different

factors: vaccination history, age, sex, and knowledge of vaccination was evaluated. Time since vaccination as shown in **(Tables 5–7)**: The immunity was highest shortly after vaccination and declined over time. In young children (Group A), recent vaccination significantly improved seroprotection ($p=0.042$). In older groups (B & C), immunity also declined with time but without statistical significance. The data in **Table (5)** shows a higher proportion of seropositive individuals (44%, and 48%) were found in the more recent time spans (1 mo-1 yr, and 2-3 yrs), respectively, while seronegative individuals was more equally distributed, with a higher proportion (37.5%) in the longest time span (4 years). This suggests that for Group A, more recent vaccination is linked to better protection. One study was agreed with our study reported that immunity levels peak in early childhood, with the highest mean antibody levels observed in children aged 1-2 years (0.59 IU/mL) and 6-7 years (0.64 IU/mL). A decline in antibody levels was noted after age 20, with adults showing a susceptibility rate of 65.4%⁽⁸⁾.

The seropositivity of IgG as seen in **Table (6)** was decreased with increasing the time after diphtheria toxoid, it was (12.5%) after passing a greater than 9 years, however, there was no a statistically significant association ($P\text{-value}= 0.8$). A study has been agreed with our finding as the duration of protective immunity varies, with a decline to 0.1 IU/ml observed approximately 10.3 years after three doses⁽⁶⁾.

The seropositivity of IgG after the 3rd dose as seen in **Table (7)** was very low when the time was ≥ 19 years, compared to those after 10–12 years (4.8% vs 38%), respectively. However, there was no a statistically significant association ($P=0.6$). This indicates a significant decline in immunity over time. A study was agreed with our finding was conducted in Singapore, where 92% of adults had at least basic protection against diphtheria, with a significant decline in seroprevalence observed in older age groups⁽²⁶⁾.

A chi-square test assessing if sex (Male/Female) was associated with having reliable seroprotection (≥ 0.1 IU/mL), as seen in **Table (8)**. The proportions of males and females in the "No Reliable Protection" (38.5% vs. 61.5%) and "Reliable Protection" (43.8% vs. 56.2%) groups are very similar to their overall distribution in the sample (41.6% vs. 58.4%). The result was not a statistically significant ($p=0.4$). However, the females lacked seroprotection more often than men. Similar study conducted by⁽²⁷⁾, which might be explained, in part, by gender-specific immune responses following vaccination.

Group E (oldest) showed unexpectedly higher protection, possibly due to natural exposure in youth, while Group D (middle-aged) showed poorer immunity, likely from cohort or vaccine schedule effects as shown in **Table (9)**. One study was agreed with our study conducted in six European countries and Israel reported that group E (oldest) has been a higher protection levels may stem from natural exposure to diphtheria in earlier life stages, as indicated by studies showing that older populations often retain some immunity due to past infections⁽²⁸⁾. Conversely, middle-aged adults (Group D) who showed weaker immunity, potentially due to declining vaccine effectiveness in their cohort or different childhood vaccination schedules^(6,18).

Most respondents (88–93%) had positive attitudes toward vaccination, as shown in **Table (10)**. However, a notable minority (22.3%) do not favor mandatory vaccination programs by the Ministry of Health. The high overall positive attitude is encouraging for vaccination campaigns. The significant opposition to mandatory programs highlights a potential area for public health communication strategies to address concerns and build trust, rather than relying solely on mandates. A study conducted by⁽²⁹⁾ similar to our study in which (92%) believe vaccinations are essential for child protection, with 86% considering them safe. One study reported that the attitude of health professionals is more positive, with only 2.2% of

them being against vaccinations, compared to 16.5% of the general public⁽³⁰⁾.

Table (11): This table presents the results of a one-way ANOVA test that compares the mean IgG antibody levels across five age groups. Null Hypothesis (H_0): The five age groups' mean IgG levels are identical. Alternative Hypothesis (H_1): The mean IgG level varies for at least one age group. The mean IgG antibody levels in the five age groups did not differ statistically significantly, according to the one-way ANOVA results ($F(4, 264) = 0.2625$, $p = 0.9018$). In comparison to within-group variance, the F-statistic = 0.2625 shows a very slight difference in means between age groups. We came to the conclusion that the null hypothesis could not be rejected. The five age groups' IgG levels do not differ in a way that was a statistically significant. Post-hoc testing is typically not necessary because the ANOVA result ($p = 0.90$) indicates that there was no significant difference between the age groups overall.

Numerous studies have identified substantial differences, frequently indicating a reduction in antibody levels in older persons or specific patterns of immunity depending on age, refuting the assertion that diphtheria IgG levels do not change statistically between five age groups. While some studies show no statistically significant difference between age groups, others point out that younger groups have stronger protection or that older groups or particular age ranges (e.g., 20-30 years) may have weaker protective immunity^(32,33).

A multiple logistic regression model as seen in **Table (12)** confirmed that age group, sex, maternal education, dose category, and post-vaccine symptoms were not statistically significant predictors of seroprotection status ($p > 0.05$).

CONCLUSION:

Protective immunity against diphtheria remains inadequate in Aden governorate, Yemen. Immunity gradually deteriorates with time, which highlights the importance of booster doses. Unlike other studies, this cohort's demographic characteristics were not accurately predicted. The high degree of broad vaccination acceptability may be encouraging, but opposition to mandates calls for more community involvement. Ongoing sero-surveillance should be implemented to monitor population immunity.

Recommendations: Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations have been proposed:

- Booster vaccination schedules should be implemented to maintain protective antibody levels, especially for older children, adolescents, and young adults (Groups C and D).
- Develop and implement community-based health education programs.
- Regularly measure population antibody titers to detect deteriorating immunity early.

Limitations: This study was limited to Aden governorate and may not represent the entire Yemeni population. Recall bias regarding vaccination history is possible but depends on what the participants said and on immunization cards. Antibody measurements were limited to ELISA; functional assays (neutralization tests) were not performed.

Acknowledgment: Great thank to my students of Medical Laboratory, Faculty of Medicine & Health Sciences, Aden University: Amal Khaled Salem, Heba Mansour Abdo, Rim Mohammed Ali, Wessal Habeeb Hassen, Abdullah Bin Abdullah Mohammed, Dayan Mohsen Ahmed, Redhwan Munassar Saleh, Salma Al-Ryah Mohammed, Sarah Gameel Radman, and Ibrahim Abdul-Qium Qaid.

Conflict of Interest: None

REFERENCES:

1. Zakikhany K, Efstratiou A. Diphtheria in Europe: current problems and new challenges. *Future microbiology*. 2012 May 1;7(5):595-607. <https://doi.org/10.2217/fmb.12.24>.
2. Chaudhary A, Pandey S. *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*. <https://europepmc.org/article/nbk/nbk559015>.
3. Zasada AA, Rastawicki W, Rokosz N, Jagielski M. Seroprevalence of diphtheria toxoid IgG antibodies in children, adolescents and adults in Poland. *BMC Infectious Diseases*. 2013 Nov 19;13(1):551. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2334-13-551>.
4. Cho BH, Acosta AM, Leidner AJ, Faulkner AE, Zhou F. Tetanus, diphtheria and acellular pertussis (Tdap) vaccine for prevention of pertussis among adults aged 19 years and older in the United States: A cost-effectiveness analysis. *Preventive medicine*. 2020 May 1;134:106066. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ypmed.2020.106066>.
5. Dragomirescu CC, Coldea IL, Ilie A, Stănescu A, Ungureanu V, Popa MI. Seroprevalence study of anti-diphtheria antibodies in two age-groups of Romanian adults. *Roum Arch Microbiol Immunol*. 2014 Jan 1;73(1-2):18-24. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/269771656>.
6. Kitamura N, Bahkali K, Quilty BJ, Edwards T, Toizumi M, Yoshida LM. Waning rate of immunity and duration of protective immunity against diphtheria toxoid as a function of age and number of doses: Systematic review and quantitative data analysis. *Human Vaccines & Immunotherapeutics*. 2022 Nov 30;18(6):2099700. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21645515.2022.2099700>.
7. Bhagat S, Grover SS, Gupta N, Roy RD, Khare S. Persistence of *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* in Delhi & National Capital Region (NCR). *Indian Journal of Medical Research*. 2015 Oct 1;142(4):459-61. DOI: 10.4103/0971-5916.169212.
8. Yusoff AF, Mohd Sharani ZZ, Kee CC, Md Iderus NH, Md Zamri AS, Nagalingam T, Mohamad Bashaabidin MS, Wan Ibadullah WA, Ghazali SM, Yusof AY, Ching YM. Seroprevalence of diphtheria toxoid IgG antibodies in the Malaysian population. *BMC Infectious Diseases*. 2021 Jun 16;21(1):581. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-021-06285-3>.
9. Moghalles SA, Aboasba BA, Alamad MA, Khader YS. Epidemiology of diphtheria in Yemen, 2017-2018: surveillance data analysis. *JMIR public health and surveillance*. 2021 Jun 2;7(6):e27590. <https://preprints.jmir.org/preprint/27590>.
10. Ahmad OB, Boschi-Pinto C, Lopez AD, Murray CJ, Lozano R, Inoue M. Age standardization of rates: a new WHO standard. Geneva: World Health Organization. 2001 Jan 1;9(10):1-4. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/203609941>.
11. Mohammed AR, Redwan EM, Almehdar HA. Status of diphtheria immunity among Saudi population. *J Pure and Applied Microbiol*. 2017 Mar 1;11:31-5. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/315946371>.

12. Badell E, Alharazi A, Criscuolo A, Almoayed KA, Lefrancq N, Bouchez V, Guglielmini J, Hennart M, Carmi-Leroy A, Zidane N, Pascal-Perrigault M. Ongoing diphtheria outbreak in Yemen: a cross-sectional and genomic epidemiology study. *The Lancet Microbe*. 2021 Aug 1;2(8):e386-96. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2666-5247\(21\)00094-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2666-5247(21)00094-X).
13. Dhanasekran AR, Periasamy A, Balakrishnan K, Chandran K. Increase in cases of Diphtheria in Europe among asylum-seekers. *Global Biosecurity*. 2023 Feb 20;5. <https://doi.org/10.31646/gbio.184>.
14. Aaqil SI, Ochani S, Al Hasibuzzaman M. Recent outbreak of diphtheria in Pakistan; short communication. *Annals of Medicine and Surgery*. 2023 Jun 1;85(6):3243-4. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/MS9.0000000000000832>.
15. Madhavi BR, Deva A, Reddy MM, Beena PM, Kumar SV. Seroprevalence of diphtheria IgG antibodies among 5–20 years old in diphtheria affected regions during 2018–19: Evidence in support of the revised National Vaccine Policy for diphtheria in India. *Clinical Epidemiology and Global Health*. 2024 Jan 1;25:101480. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cegh.2023.101480>
16. Khetsuriani N, Zaika O, Slobodanyk L, Scobie HM, Cooley G, Dimitrova SD, Stewart B, Geleishvili M, Allahverdiyeva V, O'Connor P, Huseynov S. Diphtheria and tetanus seroepidemiology among children in Ukraine, 2017. *Vaccine*. 2022 Mar 15;40(12):1810-20. doi: [10.1016/j.vaccine.2022.02.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2022.02.006).
17. Le HT, Do TH, Dao TA, Hoang TT, Nguyen BT, Le TL, Nguyen DL, Yoshida LM, Le XH, Le HQ, Ton TT. Seroprevalence of anti-diphtheria toxoid antibody and implications for vaccination policy in Vietnam's South-central coast: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Infectious Diseases*. 2024 Aug 12;24(1):813. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-024-09688-0>.
18. Swart EM, Van Gageldonk PG, De Melker HE, Van Der Klis FR, Berbers GA, Mollema L. Long-term protection against diphtheria in the Netherlands after 50 years of vaccination: results from a seroepidemiological study. *PLoS One*. 2016 Feb 10;11(2):e0148605. doi: [10.1371/journal.pone.0148605](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0148605).
19. Nassar AA, Al-Amad MA, Ghaleb YA. Risk factors for diphtheria in Sana'a, Yemen, 2019: a matched case-control study. *IJID Regions*. 2022 Mar 1;2:40-4. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijregi.2021.11.010>.
20. Naumann P, Hagedorn HJ, Paatz R. Diphtheria immunity and its epidemiological significance. *Deutsche Medizinische Wochenschrift (1946)*. 1983 Jul 1;108(28-29):1090-6. doi: [10.1055/S-2008-1069698](https://doi.org/10.1055/S-2008-1069698).
21. Nanthavong N, Black AP, Nouanthong P, Souvannaso C, Vilivong K, Muller CP, Goossens S, Quet F, Buisson Y. Diphtheria in Lao PDR: insufficient coverage or ineffective vaccine? *PloS one*. 2015 Apr 24;10(4):e0121749. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0121749>.

22. Yang JJ, Chung Y, Kim H, Ko DH, Hwang SH, Oh HB. Retrospection of Anti–Blood Group Antibody Proficiency Testing Data Using the Geometric Mean and Standard Deviation. *American Journal of Clinical Pathology*. 2020 Mar 9;153(4):530-6. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcp/aqz187>.
23. Desgagnés JS, Désy O, Thivierge MP, Marcoux M, Béland S, De Serres SA. SARS-CoV-2 antibody levels that confer immune protection based on neutralization of the Omicron Variant. *Transplantation*. 2023 Jun 1;107(6):e184-5. DOI: 10.1097/TP.0000000000004596.
24. Zhang S, Ma P, Orzechowski M, Lemmer A, Rzasa K, Bagnall J, Barkho S, Chen M, He L, Neitupski R, Tran V. High-throughput neutralization and serology assays reveal correlated but highly variable humoral immune responses in a large population of individuals infected with SARS-CoV-2 in the US between March and August 2020. *MBio*. 2023 Apr 25;14(2):e03523-22. <https://doi.org/10.1128/mbio.03523-22>.
25. Uysal BB, Yavuzer S, Islamoglu MS, Cengiz M. Measurement of antibody levels in patients with COVID-19 over time by immunofluorescence assay: a longitudinal observational study. *Journal of International Medical Research*. 2022 Jan;50(1):03000605211069279. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03000605211069279>.
26. Ang LW, James L, Goh KT. Prevalence of diphtheria and tetanus antibodies among adults in Singapore: a national serological study to identify most susceptible population groups. *Journal of Public Health*. 2016 Mar 1;38(1):99-105. <https://doi.org/10.1093/pubmed/fdv011>.
27. Völzke H, Kloker KM, Kramer A, Guertler L, Dören M, Baumeister SE, Hoffmann W, John U. Susceptibility to diphtheria in adults: prevalence and relationship to gender and social variables. *Clinical microbiology and infection*. 2006 Oct 1;12(10):961-7. DOI: [10.1111/j.1469-0691.2006.01477.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-0691.2006.01477.x).
28. Di Giovine P, Kafatos G, Nardone A, Andrews N, Ölander RM, Alfarone G, Broughton K, Cohen D, Kriz B, Mikova I, O'FLANAGAN D. Comparative seroepidemiology of diphtheria in six European countries and Israel. *Epidemiology & Infection*. 2013 Jan;141(1):132-42. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0950268812000210>.
29. Ahmed NJ, Alrawili AS, Alkhawaja FZ. The Public Attitudes, Concerns and Behaviors towards Children Vaccination. *JPRI*, 2021; 33(13): 39-43. <http://www.sdiarticle4.com/review-history/66290>.
30. Paulić P. *Razlike između zdravstvenih djelatnika i opće populacije o informiranosti i stavovima o cijepljenju* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Zagreb. School of Medicine. Chair of Medical Sociology and Health Economics). <https://urn.nsk.hr/urn:nbn:hr:105:044820>
31. Hadzhieva S, Chamova R, Ivanova E, Radeva N, Rohova M, Mihaylov NL, Paunov T, Kolarova M, Pancheva R. Attitudes towards mandatory vaccinations during the COVID-19 pandemic in Bulgaria. *European Journal of Public Health*. 2022 Oct 1;32. DOI: [10.1093/eurpub/ckac130.229](https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/ckac130.229).

32. Ciftçi A, Tekeli ME. Antibody levels to diphtheria in various community segments. *Mikrobiyoloji Bulteni*. 2002 Jan 1;36(1):15-21. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/12476762/>.
33. Wanlapakorn N, Suntronwong N, Kanokudom S, Assawakosri S, Vichaiwattana P, Klinfueng S, Wongsrisang L, Thongmee T, Aeemjinda R, Khanarat N, Srimuan D. Seroprevalence of antibodies against diphtheria, tetanus, and pertussis across various age groups during the post-COVID-19 pandemic period in Chonburi Province, Thailand. *Heliyon*. 2024 Nov 15;10(21). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e39889>.